

Quantitative Evaluation of xAI Methods for Multivariate Time Series - A Case Study for a CNN-based MI Detection Model*

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Abstract. This paper presents an evaluation framework for xAI methods that is tailored for multivariate time series data. The framework includes three evaluation approaches encompassing a stability analysis, consistency analysis, and truthfulness analysis. The stability analysis investigates the consistency of explanations provided by a single xAI method for similar inputs. In the truthfulness analysis, the meaningfulness of explanations provided by an xAI method is examined. The consistency analysis assesses the similarity of explanations generated by different xAI methods. We demonstrate the application of these evaluation techniques using a medical use case involving electrocardiogram (ECG) data. Specifically, we evaluate the explanations of two popular xAI methods, LRP and SHAP, for a convolutional neural network (CNN) that detects myocardial infarctions (MI). We will show that LRP and SHAP both provide meaningful explanations for this model, with SHAP being slightly more truthful. On the other hand, our stability analysis will reveal that LRP is more stable than SHAP for the investigated use case. Finally, the consistency analysis will allow us to demonstrate that LRP and SHAP partly disagree in explaining the leads and time intervals most relevant for the MI detection model towards its classification.

Keywords: xAI · explainability · interpretability · quantitative evaluation · truthfulness · stability · consistency · multivariate time series.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become prevalent in various aspects of our lives. Industries across healthcare, finance, transportation, and entertainment are undergoing a transformative shift through AI.

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However, as AI becomes increasingly complex, the decisions of AI models become difficult or even impossible to understand. This lack of interpretability raises concerns about trust, accountability, and potential biases inherent in the underlying AI-based systems. In critical domains such as medical diagnosis or autonomous driving, the understanding of model decisions is not just desirable but essential for ensuring safety, reliability, and ethical use of AI. In response to this challenge, the field of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (xAI) has emerged, aiming to bridge the gap between the decision-making process of AI models and human understanding. Various xAI methods have been developed such as Layer-wise Relevance Propagation (LRP) [4], Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) [10], and Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME) [14]. These xAI methods offer promising solutions, but their effectiveness in providing meaningful and reliable explanations needs to be rigorously evaluated.

However, evaluating the effectiveness of xAI methods is not a straightforward task. The definitions of *meaningful* and *reliable* explanations depend on the specific application context. Furthermore, xAI explanations may differ from those of human experts, but that does not necessarily make them incorrect. For example, an AI model trained to detect beaches in images may focus on waves (known as the Clever Hans phenomenon [8]), while a human may focus solely on the beach itself. In this case, an explanation that highlights the waves would be valuable for understanding the model’s decision-making process, although it deviates from how human experts may draw conclusions. In this illustrative example in which the AI model decision-making diverges from that of human decision-making, it becomes imperative to employ mechanisms that analyze xAI methods and ensure that they genuinely elucidate the decision-making processes of the AI models, rather than merely producing random and impractical explanations. Another challenge arises when different xAI methods provide significantly different explanations. In this scenario, it is not clear which method explains the AI model best.

To overcome these challenges, this paper presents and applies three types of quantitative evaluation approaches for xAI methods. First, we propose a *stability analysis* (see Section 3.3) that investigates whether a single xAI method provides similar explanations for similar input, and, thus, can be considered stable and reliable. Second, we demonstrate how to conduct a *consistency analysis* (see Section 3.4), which assesses the similarity of explanations generated by different xAI methods, and, therefore, allows to provide evidence that the methods accurately explain the decision-making of the AI model due to coherence. Finally, we perform a *truthfulness analysis* (see Section 3.2), which examines if an investigated xAI method provides meaningful explanations.

The evaluation approaches presented in this paper are tailored for models working with multivariate time series data. Although research has been conducted in the field of evaluating xAI methods, a standardized approach is still lacking. Furthermore, only a few evaluation approaches specifically focus on AI models for multivariate time series. Therefore, this paper aims to explore the above-mentioned evaluation techniques specifically tailored for multivariate time

series. To illustrate our findings, we will demonstrate the proposed analyses and present the corresponding evaluation results using a use case from the medical domain that demonstrates the need for and the application of the evaluation techniques. Precisely, we will quantitatively evaluate the capability of the xAI methods LRP and SHAP to explain the decision-making of a CNN-based model that recognizes myocardial infarctions (MIs) based on multivariate electrocardiogram (ECG) data. A myocardial infarction, commonly known as a heart attack, occurs when blood flow to a part of the heart is blocked, leading to tissue damage or death due to lack of oxygen. To detect abnormalities indicative of a myocardial infarction, an ECG is a frequently employed non-invasive diagnostic test that records the electrical activity of the heart. Typically, an ECG consists of multiple leads, each providing a unique perspective on the heart’s electrical activity, aiding in diagnosing and localising MIs and other cardiac abnormalities.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. We first provide some background which includes a formal definition of multivariate time series data and a description of the use case that will guide us throughout the paper. Then, we provide an overview of related work within the field of quantitative evaluation of xAI methods. We thereby focus on presenting work concerning the stability, consistency and truthfulness of explanations. Thereafter, we present our methodology in Section 3. We show explanation approaches for multivariate time series data that attribute relevance scores to features. Then, we discuss the truthfulness, stability and consistency analysis tailored for multivariate times series data. We provide step-by-step instructions on how to apply these analyses for the presented use case. Afterwards, we provide and discuss experimental results of all three analyses in Sections 4 and 5 respectively, before concluding the paper in Section 6.

2 Background & State of the Art

2.1 Multivariate Time Series

A multivariate time series is a sequence of observations where each observation consists of multiple variables recorded over time. It can be defined as

$$T_{n,m} := (t_{ij})_{i=1,\dots,n;j=1,\dots,m} \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of channels per point in time and m corresponds to the total number of points in time. For instance, a 12-lead electrocardiogram is a multivariate time series as for each point in time, there are $n = 12$ different variables corresponding to the 12 so-called leads.

2.2 MI Detection Use Case

To practically demonstrate the evaluation methods for xAI techniques on multivariate time series data proposed in this paper, we will utilize a real-world AI-based application in which xAI methods are part of the system to explain

the AI-based decision-making and to enhance the system’s interpretability and users’ trust. Precisely, we have integrated an AI model into an emergency call (eCall) system to automatically detect emergencies by analyzing sensor data representing multivariate time series. The corresponding eCall system was developed in context of the EMYNOS³ project and is described in [13, 7]. In addition, the AI-based extensions utilized in this paper have been previously presented in [6].

The CNN-based MI detector. As an illustrative example of an emergency to be detected by the eCall system, we have trained a one-dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to identify myocardial infarctions based on 12-lead ECG data. The CNN model is an adapted version of the CNN architecture discussed in [6] and is depicted in Figure 1. We applied the Keras Hyperband tuner to optimize the filter and kernel sizes of the convolutional layers, as well as the dropout rates and the number of units of the dense layer. For training the model, we used the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01 and incorporated early stopping after 30 iterations with no decrease in the validation loss. The resulting CNN model has an accuracy of 96%, a precision of 93%, and a recall of 95% on the PTB-XL test set.

Fig. 1: Architecture of model showing convolutional (blue), dropout (yellow), pooling (green) and dense (grey) layers, alongside with output dimensions. The kernel sizes are shown below the respective layers and the dropout rates within the dropout layers.

The PTB-XL benchmarking dataset. To train and evaluate the CNN model for MI detection, we used a benchmarking dataset called PTB-XL [23], which originally consists of 10-second-long ECG recordings from 18869 patients. Detailed information about the statistics of the dataset and the preprocessing applied prior to training the MI detector is already described in our previous work [6]. As explained in this paper, we employed a windowing approach to overcome an unbalancing issue towards the target class MI. However, the resulting modifications of the applied preprocessing only affect the distribution of the train and validation sets of the PTB-XL dataset, resulting in two sets that are

³ <https://www.emynos.eu>, as of 21/02/2024

almost balanced for the two classes MI and **Non-MI**⁴. In contrast, to still reflect the expected original distribution, the test set consisting of 1187 samples remains unaltered and unbalanced with 75.48% of ECGs belonging to class **Non-MI** and 24.52% belonging to class MI. As a result of the implemented windowing approach described in [6], the CNN model expects ECGs of only 2.5-second length as input⁵. Therefore, considering the 100Hz frequency rate within the PTB-XL dataset, a single preprocessed 12-lead ECG with a length of 2.5 seconds used as input to the model can be defined according to Eq. 1 as follows:

$$ECG := T_{12,250} = (t_{ij})_{i=1,\dots,12;j=1,\dots,250} \quad (2)$$

The importance of reliable and meaningful explanations. As the system deals with emergencies, its accountability is of utmost importance. Alongside good performance results, explanations provided by xAI methods can foster trust in the system. As there are multiple xAI methods that can be applied to models working with multivariate time series data, the evaluation of such methods for this specific application is needed to 1) select which one best explains the system and should therefore be incorporated and 2) to build trust that the generated explanations are indeed valuable to understand the system’s behavior.

2.3 Related Work

In this section, we provide an overview of the related work that has been conducted in the field of quantitative evaluation of xAI methods. For a detailed overview of work related to xAI for time series classification, we refer to the survey from Theissler et al. [20]. According to Nauta et al. [11], the amount of work on evaluating xAI methods has increased in recent years, although in 2020 around 33% of papers introducing or applying an xAI technique still only use anecdotal evidence rather than quantitative evaluation techniques. In their structured review, they define twelve desirable properties that describe the quality of an explanation and propose to use them to categorize evaluation techniques. However, to match the scope of this paper, the following subsection will only discuss work that is related to the truthfulness, stability, and consistency of explanations as defined in Section 1.

Related work on the stability of explanations. Alvarez-Melis et al. [1] studies the stability of explanations for image classifiers but use the term robustness instead. To assess the stability, they propose to use an estimate of the Lipschitz constant. Therefore, a meaningful neighborhood of samples needs to

⁴ The exact distribution of the train and validation set is not relevant for this paper, as only the test set samples are used for evaluating the xAI methods. Hence, we refer the interested reader to [6] for more details in this regard.

⁵ In case ECGs longer than 2.5s are supplied to the system, only a subwindow of 2.5s is used as input to the model (e.g. this is the case for all ECGs from the original test set). An analysis on the selection process of such a subwindow can be found in [6].

be defined. They demonstrated their proposed stability analysis for various xAI methods such as LIME, SHAP, LRP, Saliency maps, Gradient*Input, Integrated Gradients, and Occlusion Sensitivity applied to different image classifiers trained on benchmarking datasets from the UCI Machine Learning Repository⁶. Building on the stability analysis proposed by Alvaraz-Melis et al., Saarela et al. [15] evaluate an image classification model for detecting skin cancer. Additionally, they investigate whether the same images as input to the model result in the same explanations in different runs. This approach is part of our stability analysis described in Section 3.3. Finally, they investigate the fidelity of the model that can be applied to a surrogate model in order to assess how closely the surrogate reflects the original model. We won't apply this evaluation technique as we use the xAI method LRP which does not work with a surrogate model.

In contrast to the above-mentioned works that present their approaches and experimental results, Amparore et al. [2] provide a dedicated Python framework for evaluating xAI methods, called LEAF⁷. Besides the reiteration similarity of explanations, they propose to evaluate the conciseness, fidelity, concordance, and prescriptivity. They demonstrate their evaluation framework by presenting results for LIME and SHAP. For this purpose, they use different classifiers on different benchmarking datasets, interpreting all data as tabular data. As the MI detection model that we use in our work expects multivariate time series which has one more dimension than tabular data, we cannot utilize the proposed framework to evaluate xAI techniques for our model. To the best of our knowledge, there is no work yet that evaluates the stability of explanations for models working with multivariate time series.

Related work on the consistency of explanations. There are only few research efforts that compare the ranking of feature importance scores attributed by different xAI methods quantitatively. For instance, in the work from Ancona et al. [3] about a polynomial-time approximation of Shapley values, the Spearman rank correlation is used as an evaluation metric to assess the agreement of two methods on the ranking of features to show that their novel approach outperforms the classical approach for calculating Shapely values. Duell et al. [5] compare the consistency of explanations generated by SHAP and LIME by counting the cases in which the top k ranked features agree for different values for k . We will adapt this approach for multivariate time series in this paper.

Related work on the truthfulness of explanations. While we could not identify relevant work specifically tailored for multivariate time series data for the two evaluation techniques discussed above, more research has been conducted on how to adapt the truthfulness analysis to xAI methods for multivariate time series. However, there exist various terms that describe the truthfulness analysis: Turbé et al. [21] refer to it as *relevance identification*, Theissler et al. [20] call

⁶ <https://archive.ics.uci.edu>, as of 21/02/2024

⁷ <https://github.com/amparore/leaf>, as of 22/2/2024

it *faithfulness* and Samek et al. [16] as well as Schlegel et al. [17] use the terms *perturbation process* and perturbation analysis, respectively. We adopted the terminology from Veerappa et al. [22] who call it the *truthfulness* of explanations.

Samek et al. [16] introduced a region perturbation process to evaluate generated explanations in the form of heat maps for image classifiers. This approach has been adapted by Schlegel et al. [17] for classifiers working with univariate time series. In their work they present two perturbation techniques for univariate time series as a basis for the truthfulness analysis. They benchmark five xAI methods (LIME, LRP, DeepLIFT, Saliency Map and SHAP) on nine benchmarking datasets from the UCR Time Series Classification Archive. Other research efforts build upon this evaluation technique for multivariate time series data by adapting the perturbation techniques needed for this evaluation [18, 22]. Furthermore, Turbé et al. [21] propose two novel metrics for assessing the truthfulness (referred to as “relevance identification”): an area under the curve, which indicates the normalised difference in scores relative to the fraction of modified points, and an F1 score that takes both, the ability of xAI methods to identify meaningful points with highest and smallest relevance, respectively, into account. They present results for six explanation methods (DeepLift, GradShap, Integrated Gradients, KernelShap, DeepLiftShap, Shapley Value Sampling) for three AI models on three datasets of multivariate time series. Finally, Nguyen et al. [12] propose to use referee classifiers that measure the impact of explanation-based perturbations and thereby the faithfulness of explanations. They demonstrate their approach on six univariate time series benchmarking datasets from UCR. Serramazza et al. [19] extend this to the case of multivariate time series classification tasks by translating them to univariate ones, allowing them to use the same evaluation framework.

In summary, the quantitative evaluation of the stability and consistency of xAI methods applied to models operating on multivariate time series data has not yet been sufficiently addressed. Therefore, we aim to close this gap by proposing a stability and consistency analysis tailored for multivariate time series data in this paper. Besides, we will conduct the truthfulness analysis proposed by Schlegel et al. [17]. To demonstrate the practicability of our proposed evaluation techniques, we will showcase them using a real-world example based on multivariate ECG data.

3 Methodology

In the following, we will introduce our approaches to quantitatively evaluate xAI methods for AI models operating on multivariate time series data. We will start by formally defining explanations for multivariate time series data. Subsequently, we will present the rationale and objectives of the performed stability, consistency, and truthfulness analyses. Since we intend to demonstrate the proposed evaluation techniques using explanations of the ECG-based MI classification model (see Section 2.2), we will consistently refer to the specific implementation

of these techniques with respect to this use case. An overview of the basic process of each of the three analyses is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Flow chart demonstrating the basic process of each of the three analyses (truthfulness, stability and consistency) performed w.r.t the use case.

3.1 Explanations for Time Series Data

Explanation methods can be divided based on the scale of their interpretation [9]: Local explanation methods provide insights about the prediction of a particular instance, whereas global explanation methods provide an overall understanding of the model’s decision-making process across the dataset. In this paper, we will focus on local explanation methods that generate relevance scores for input variables. For each time series $T_{n,m}$ that is input to the AI model, these xAI methods provide an explanation

$$R_{n,m} = (r_{ij})_{i=1,\dots,n,j=1,\dots,m} \quad (3)$$

which is a time series itself. We will refer to this time series of relevance scores as the *base explanation*. For each point j in time and each observation i per point in time, the score r_{ij} determines the relevance of variable t_{ij} for the model’s decision towards a specific class. Hence, for our exploratory use case, this value indicates the relevance towards detecting MI in the respective ECG. An example of a base explanation is shown in Figure 3a as a heatmap overlaying the explained ECG.

In order to compare explanations from similar time series, as we will do in the stability analysis (see Section 3.3), we compute contributions of relevance

scores towards the model’s decision for a specific class: We first set all negative scores to zero as these reflect negative relevance, i.e. relevance against the class. We then apply a unit normalization. This modification results in a time series of contributions:

$$\hat{R}_{n,m} := (c_{ij})_{i=1,\dots,n,j=1,\dots,m}, \text{ with } 0 \leq c_{ij} \leq 1 \text{ and } \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m c_{ij} = 1 \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3: Three explanations inferred from the base explanation generated by LRP. All scores are scaled to be within $[0, 1]$ for visualization purposes.

Inferred relevance of channels and time intervals. Relevance scores for each channel (called *lead* in ECGs) and for time intervals can be derived from the base explanation by averaging relevance scores across channels or time intervals, respectively. Examples are depicted in Figure 3c and Figure 3b as heatmaps overlaying the explained ECG. The allocation of relevance scores per channel and per time interval allows to rank the channels and time intervals with respect to their relevance. This allows to easily assess whether two xAI methods provide similar explanations by comparing their ranking of channels and time intervals.

We will make use of this in the consistency analysis (see Section 3.4). Figure 4 depicts the relationship between the explanation types and the three analyses that we perform.

3.2 Truthfulness Analysis

In the truthfulness analysis, the veracity of explanations is investigated by assessing the change of performance when modifying the most relevant features. A decrease in the model’s performance in predicting the correct class is expected if an xAI method assigns meaningful relevance scores with respect to the model’s decision. On the other hand, when modifying random features, this decrease is expected to be less significant. We follow the proposal by Veerappa et al. [22] and set 10% of values in a time series to zero⁸ that are 1) among the most relevant according to an xAI method or 2) randomly selected. For our use case, we evaluate the change of the model’s accuracy when predicting an ECG of class MI before and after the modification. We only assess ECGs of class MI as positive relevance scores reflect the model’s decision toward this class. For each xAI method, we proceed as follows:

1. For the subset of ECGs in the test set that belong to class MI, we compute the proportion of correctly classified ECGs.
2. For each of these ECGs, we then set 10% of data points to zero by
 - (a) selecting those data points that are most relevant according to the xAI method for the model’s decision toward MI, i.e. showing the highest relevance scores and being greater than zero.
 - (b) selecting random data points. We repeat the random selection 1000 times to account for variability and reduce the impact of outliers.
3. For both approaches of selecting data points that are being modified, we compute the proportion of correctly classified ECGs within the resulting modified sets of ECGs. For the case of random selections of data points, we compute an average accuracy.
4. We can now compare the difference of the model’s performance in predicting the correct class with and without modification. The corresponding results for our MI use case are presented in Section 4.1.

3.3 Stability Analysis

In the stability analysis, we investigate whether an xAI method provides similar explanations for similar input. The more this holds true, the more we consider the xAI method to be stable. For this evaluation, we need a metric to measure the distance of two instances that are input to the model as well as the distance of two corresponding explanations. As the input and the corresponding explanation are both two-dimensional and can be interpreted as matrices, we make use of a

⁸ The zeroing out of values can be justified with the baseline of an ECG that is at zero voltage. For other datasets a different value may be a better choice.

Fig. 4: Relationship between the generation of explanations and their evaluation, demonstrating that the analyses are based on different types of explanations.

metric that measures the distance of two matrices. Precisely, we use the metric that is induced by the Frobenius-Norm $\|\cdot\|_F$, i.e. for two time series $A_{n,m}$, $B_{n,m}$ we define their distance by

$$d(A_{n,m}, B_{n,m}) := \|A_{n,m} - B_{n,m}\|_F := \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m |a_{ij} - b_{ij}|^2}. \quad (5)$$

Leveraging this distance metric, we conduct the following two investigations.

1) Examine the stability of non-deterministic xAI methods. Since the model provides the same output for the same input, ideally the explanation for the model’s decision on that input should also be the same in different runs. This requirement is not redundant as some xAI methods (e.g. LIME and SHAP) incorporate stochastic processes or random initialization, resulting in varying explanations. Therefore, we examine whether the same input yields the same explanations in subsequent runs. Specifically, we generate n explanations E_1, \dots, E_n for each time series of the test set and calculate the average pairwise distance of these explanations, i.e. we compute

$$\frac{2}{n \cdot (n-1)} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n d(E_i, E_j) \quad (6)$$

where the factor in front of the sum is to compute the average of the $n \cdot (n-1)/2$ pairwise distances. An xAI method that always produces the same explanation for the same input and model would have an average pairwise distance of zero.

2) Analyze the stability of temporally shifted time series. We further investigate how coherent explanations on temporally shifted time series are. For this purpose, we divide a time series into segments such that two subsequent segments share a segment of some predefined length. To be more precise, for a time series $T_{n,m}$ of length m we define a subsequence

$$T_{n,r:s} := (t_{ij})_{i=1,\dots,n;j=r,\dots,s} \text{ with } 1 \leq r \leq s \leq m, \quad (7)$$

Fig. 5: Process of stability evaluation in which an ECG of length 1000 is divided into subsequences of length 250. Then, explanations are generated and subsequent explanations are compared. This results in an average distance score.

starting at time r and with length $s-r+1$. Then two subsequences $T_{n,r:r+l-1}$ and $T_{n,r+k:r+l-1+k}$ of length l overlap by $l-k$ time steps for $1 \leq k \leq l \leq m-r+1$.

After dividing a time series into subsequences that overlap, we then generate explanations for each of them and compare explanations of shared parts. As the underlying time series in the shared part of two subsequent subsequences of the same time series is the same, we expect similar contributions of relevance scores in these parts. Hence, to evaluate the stability of explanations for our MI detection model, we proceed as follows. For each xAI method,

1. we first segment each 10-second long ECG sequence of the test set in subsequences of length 2.5 seconds each such that two subsequent sequences share 1.25 seconds. This segmentation results in seven ECG subsequences per ECG of the test set.
2. We generate explanations in form of relevance scores for each of the 2.5-second long ECGs by applying the xAI method.
3. For two subsequent ECGs with an overlapping part of 1.25 seconds, we extract the explanations of the overlapping part. We set all negative relevance scores to zero and then compute contributions. Furthermore, we compute the distance of these contributions with metric 5. This results in six distance scores per ECG in the test set.
4. We compute average distances per ECG in the test set by computing the mean of the six distance scores per ECG.

The process of evaluating the stability is illustrated in Figure 5.

3.4 Consistency Analysis

In the consistency analysis, we assess the similarity of explanations generated by different xAI methods. We therefore compare to what extent the xAI methods

agree, i.e. classify the same channels and the same time segments as relevant. For our MI detection model, we compare the agreement of xAI methods on relevant channels (leads) and time intervals as follows.

1. For each xAI method, we compute the relevance of each lead and for each time interval of length 0.1 seconds. We do this for each ECG in the test set as described in section 3.1.
2. We determine the k_c most relevant leads and the k_t most relevant time intervals per ECG and xAI method. We do this for each possible choice for k_c and k_t , i.e. for every $1 \leq k_c \leq 12$ and every $1 \leq k_t \leq 25$. The upper limit of 25 is due to the fact that we divide the 2.5-second long ECGs into 25 time intervals of length 0.1s.
3. For each $1 \leq k_c \leq 12$, we compare the k_c most relevant leads per ECG across xAI methods by computing intersections. We do the same with the k_t most relevant time intervals.

4 Experimental Results

After having defined the methodology for our evaluation approaches, we aim to demonstrate their practicability in the following section. To this end, we will present experimental evaluation results for the use case of ECG-based MI detection using a CNN model as described in Section 2.2. Specifically, we will employ this use case to quantitatively evaluate and compare explanations for multivariate time series data provided by the xAI methods LRP and SHAP. We make use of the LRP-epsilon method and the GradientExplainer from the Python packages `iNNvestigate`⁹ and `shap`¹⁰, respectively. All results presented in this section are based on the PTB-XL test set consisting of 1187 ECGs.

4.1 Results of the Truthfulness Analysis

Based on the original data, the MI detection model correctly predicted 92.44% of the ECGs in the test set belonging to class MI. After modification of the values in each ECG with the 10% highest relevance scores as identified by LRP and SHAP, the accuracy significantly dropped to 65.63% for each of the two xAI methods. Precisely, after performing modifications based on LRP, the prediction probability of the model for detecting MI decreased for 97.59% of the ECGs, with an average decline of 0.2755. Modifications according to the relevant features identified by SHAP yielded a decrease in prediction probability for 98.97% of the ECGs, which is slightly higher compared to LRP. The average decrease in the prediction probability for SHAP was 0.2809, being also slightly higher than for LRP.

To validate that the observed performance decline is in fact driven by the meaningfulness of the data features identified as relevant by the xAI methods,

⁹ <https://github.com/albermax/innvestigate>, as of 27/02/2024

¹⁰ <https://github.com/shap/shap>, as of 27/02/2024

Fig. 6: Distribution of model predictions before and after modification of the test set of ECGs belonging to class MI. Predictions are average values over all repetitions in the case of randomly selecting data points for modification.

we validate the results by randomly modifying data. When modifying a random selection of 10% of each ECG, the model’s accuracy even increased to an average value of 93.11%. This slightly higher accuracy could be attributed to the fact that noise was minimized by zeroing out values, resulting in slightly better predictions of the model. The distribution of model predictions before (original) and after the three types of modifications can be seen in Figure 6. The model predictions in the case of random selections of data points, are averaged values per ECG as we repeated the random selection and modification 1000 times per ECG.

In conclusion, the result of the conducted truthfulness analysis suggest that both xAI methods detect relevant data features meaningful for the CNNs prediction towards MI, with SHAP performing slightly better than LRP.

4.2 Results of the Stability Analysis

Determinism of local explanations. While LRP always provides a deterministic explanation for the same ECG and model, SHAP is generating different explanations in each run. To evaluate the variance in the non-deterministic local explanations provided by SHAP, we generated ten explanations for each ECG of the test set and computed average pairwise explanation distances according

Fig. 7: Comparison of the results of the stability analysis of the two xAI methods LRP and SHAP. The height of the bins show the number of ECGs for which the average explanation distance is within a specific range.

to Eq. 6. As result, we observed that SHAP manifests a mean distance of 0.0237 and a standard deviation of 0.0074 across the explanations generated from the test set. This is due to the random sampling that is involved when computing the SHAP explanations. Hence, LRP is more stable than SHAP according to the first stability analysis.

Stability of temporally shifted data. Results of the second stability analysis in which we analyzed whether the investigated methods provide similar explanations for similar input instances are shown in Figure 7. The bar plot compares the average explanation distances of LRP and SHAP. As we can observe, all average explanation distances are below 0.12. LRP and SHAP have approximately the same amount of ECGs with an average explanation distance below 0.04. The number of ECGs with an average explanation distance in between 0.04 and 0.06 is with approximately 800 ECGs higher for LRP than for SHAP with an approximate number of only 600 ECGs. In contrast, the number of ECGs with an average explanation distance in between 0.06 and 0.08 as well as in between 0.08 and 0.1 is higher for SHAP than for LRP. There are a few ECGs for which LRP has an average explanation distance above 0.1 but this number is negligible. Based on the gained insights provided by this analysis, we can conclude that LRP is more stable than SHAP as it manifests on average smaller explanation distances.

Fig. 8: Agreement of LRP and SHAP on the top- k -most relevant leads for $k=1$ (left), $k=2$ (center) and $k=3$ (right).

4.3 Results of the Consistency Analysis

The consistency analysis allows us to compare the explanations generated by LRP and SHAP in relation to the leads and time segments that were identified as most relevant towards an MI classification. Therefore, we will compare the identified most important leads and time segments attributed by these two xAI methods in the following.

Agreement on the most relevant leads. Figure 8 shows the consistency of the top- k -most relevant leads across these two methods for $k = 1, 2, 3$. When investigated only the most relevant lead ($k = 1$), we observed that LRP and SHAP declared the same lead as most significant towards an MI prediction in 39.2% of the cases. For the remaining 60.8% of explanations, these two methods did not agree on the most important lead. This finding is also strengthened by the distribution of the most relevant leads according to LRP and SHAP, shown in Figure 9. As we can see, both xAI methods most frequently assign the most relevance to lead V5, with SHAP doing so in approximately 28.64% of ECGs and LRP in 23%. Whereas LRP assigns with 20.01% of ECGs second most often the most importance to lead III, SHAP assigns only in 5.9% the most relevance to this lead. According to SHAP, lead V2 is on average the second most relevant lead. Furthermore, the two methods do not agree with respect to the relevance of lead aVR. In approximately 150 ECGs of the test set (12.55%), SHAP declares this lead as most relevant (third most frequently) whereas LRP is doing so in only 2.5% of ECGs.

When considering the top two most relevant leads ($k = 2$), LRP and SHAP agreed in 70.1% of explanations in at least one lead to be among the most two relevant (see Figure 8). Precisely, they agreed in 20.6% of cases in both leads and in 49.5% in exactly one out of the two leads. Furthermore, Figure 8 shows the agreement of SHAP and LRP is most of the times in between one and two out of the top three scored leads, with 37.3% and 37.6% of explanations showing an agreement of one and two, respectively ($k = 3$).

Fig. 9: Distribution of the most relevant leads according to LRP and SHAP on the PTB-XL test set.

Fig. 10: Agreement of LRP and SHAP on the top-k-most relevant time intervals for k=1 (left), k=2 (center) and k=3 (right).

Agreement on the most relevant time segments. The agreement of the two xAI methods LRP and SHAP on the top- k -most relevant time intervals for $k = 1, 2, 3$ is shown in Figure 10. It is slightly worse than that on the top most leads. Indeed, the agreement on the top most time interval is only 28.6% and the agreement of at least one of the two top most leads is with $45\% + 13.1\% = 58.1\%$ also smaller than that of the leads. LRP and SHAP agree most of the times on one or two of the top three most relevant time intervals but the agreement of the two most relevant time intervals is with 30.2% slightly lower than the agreement on the top two most relevant leads. However, the worse agreement on time intervals than on leads can be due to the fact, that there exist more time intervals than leads (25 versus 12).

In conclusion, there is to some extent consistency across explanations from LRP and SHAP. In some explanations, the two methods completely disagree on the top most relevant leads or time intervals, in others, they completely agree, and in most cases, they partly agree.

5 Discussion

After having presented the results of our three proposed and applied quantitative evaluation techniques for xAI methods, we would like to briefly discuss the implications of the obtained results for the selection of an xAI method in our investigated exemplary use case of a critical emergency communication system. Furthermore, we would like to briefly discuss to what extent the techniques presented and applied in this paper can be helpful in the development, evaluation and selection of machine learning (ML) models.

The implications of the results on the eCall use case. When deciding which xAI method to include in our critical emergency call use case, the consistency analysis indicated the partly disagreement of the investigated methods by revealing the existence of ECGs for which the two xAI methods LRP and SHAP provide highly different explanations. This inconsistency raises questions about why the most relevant leads or time intervals suggested by each method differ and which may be better suited for the application context. Especially when considering the limited time available in the emergency call system and the high level of trust and clarity demanded by the patient and medical operators to initiate optimal countermeasures, it is important to incorporate other evaluation techniques to choose one xAI method for integration that is best-suited to provide meaningful explanations. In this context, the stability analysis suggests that LRP provides more coherent explanations across time-shifted ECGs. On the other hand, the truthfulness analysis suggests that SHAP detects on average slightly more relevant features. This contradiction highlights that a definite statement about the better xAI method cannot be easily made and that trade-off between stability and truthfulness needs to be considered when selecting one of these two xAI methods into the critical application of automatically detecting

Summary and Findings of this Paper:

- Our quantitative evaluation framework allows to compare the reliability and meaningfulness of xAI explanations for models on multivariate time series.
 - The truthfulness analysis provides evidence that xAI methods identify meaningful features towards the model’s decision-making.
 - The stability analysis investigates the similarity of explanations of an xAI methods for similar data inputs, thus, assessing their reliability.
 - The consistency analysis assesses the agreement of explanations generated by different explanation methods.
- SHAP provides slightly more truthful explanations than LRP for the explored MI detection use case.
- LRP explanations are more stable compared to SHAP in the investigated application scenario.
- LRP and SHAP sometimes agree on the channels and time segments most relevant towards an MI classification, but disagree in most of the cases.
- Different xAI methods outperform each other for distinct quantitative evaluation criteria, suggesting that trade-offs (e.g. *stability vs. truthfulness*) need to be defined when deciding for the most suitable method for an application.
- Qualitative evaluation involving relevant stakeholders is suggested to define and clear trade-offs as well as to optimize XAI for the application domain.

MI and initiating corresponding emergency calls. In this context, incorporating a human and its qualitative evaluation ability in the loop can aid in the decision-making process. Users can provide qualitative feedback on the criteria that the explanations should meet for a specific application. Furthermore, they can help to define and clear trade-offs arising from the quantitative results. For example, relevant stakeholders can be involved to determine whether the stability or the truthfulness of explanations is more important in our use case. Finally, the potential of quantitative and qualitative evaluation approaches for xAI methods can be combined to find xAI methods for an application that 1) provide objectively high-quality and 2) quantitatively measurable meaningful and reliable explanations.

Utilizing the evaluation framework in model selection processes. Independent of our illustrative use case, the techniques presented in this paper can not only be used for the comparison and selection of xAI methods, but also be used during the development, evaluation, and selection of machine learning models in general. For example, the empirical insights obtained through the presented quantitative evaluation techniques can be used to tune and optimize the underlying ML model and the adapted xAI methods, resulting in highly

explainable and accountable ML models. Furthermore, the proposed evaluation framework can also be used in the ML selection process for comparing different ML model candidates most suitable for a given application. In this context, not only the model performance but also the empirically measurable explainability characteristics are considered in the selection process. For example, if two models exhibit similar performance but different results in the evaluation of their explanations, the model with better explanations, such as those that are more stable, truthful, or consistent, can be chosen. In this scenario, trade-offs between model performance and explainability may have to be defined and satisfied on an application-specific basis. However, this more holistic approach to the development and selection of ML models generally leads to the development of models that not only exhibit high performance but also manifest a high level of explainability, which enables and enhances user trust in the ML models and contributes to the ML-based application being more reliable, ethical, and trustworthy.

6 Conclusion

In this work, we proposed and applied three evaluation techniques that enable to quantitatively assess the quality of explanations for machine learning models utilizing multivariate time series data. Precisely, we adopted a truthfulness analysis, and proposed a stability and consistency analysis that are tailored for multivariate time series. To demonstrate the practicability of the presented evaluation framework, we applied these three techniques to evaluate the quality of explanations generated by the two xAI methods LRP and SHAP for a CNN model that automatically detects MIs in context of a critical emergency communication system.

Our obtained results indicate that SHAP provides slightly more meaningful explanations towards the MI detection of the investigated model, suggesting that SHAP is more truthful than LRP for the explored use case. In contrast, the stability analysis revealed that LRP explanations are more stable compared to SHAP in the investigated scenario. Furthermore, when directly comparing LRP and SHAP explanations in the consistency analysis, we found that LRP and SHAP sometimes agree on the channels and time segments most relevant towards an MI classification, but disagree in most of the cases. Therefore, we conclude to only incorporate one of the two methods in the emergency call system to avoid confusion of the patient and medical operator. However, we suggest to involve users (e.g. medical experts) and their qualitative feedback to assess the importance of each of the quality criteria, and define and satisfy the *stability vs. truthfulness* trade-off as imposed by our discussed quantitative analysis results.

In future research, we aim to explore additional xAI methods and evaluate their stability, truthfulness and consistency. We also plan to analyze different models on the same dataset, comparing their explainability with respect to the three proposed analyses. Furthermore, a standardised approach for evaluating xAI methods tailored for multivariate time series data is still missing and should be developed.

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